

Data Management Plan for the GraSP Project: Methodology for Optimal Design of Additively Manufactured Graded Lattice Structures for Impact Protection

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the GraSP (Izp-2025/1-0232) project outlines the procedures and standards for handling data throughout the project's lifecycle. It ensures that data are managed by FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), providing a data collection, storage, documentation, sharing, and preservation framework.

The project is focused on the development and experimental validation of 3D-printed graded closed-cell lattice polymer structures for impact protection. The specific aim of the project is the development of a methodology for the optimal design of graded 3D-printed energy-absorbing polymer structures. The project combines specialized software development for generating lattice structures with varying topologies, cell sizes, and wall thicknesses, manufacturing of designed lattices by fused filament fabrication, computer simulations of compressive behavior of generated structures, experimental characterization of energy absorbing properties of 3D-printed samples and validation of developed numerical models by experimental results. An optimization procedure will be employed to design structures with improved crashworthiness indexes.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Methodology for Optimal
Design of Additively
Manufactured Graded Lattice
Structures for Impact
Protection

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia, Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for the GraSP Project: Methodology for Optimal Design of Additively Manufactured Graded Lattice Structures for Impact Protection](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [Methodology for Optimal Design of Additively Manufactured Graded Lattice Structures for Impact Protection](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-04-01](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Compression tests of 3D-printed lattice structures

Experimental results of compression tests of 3D-printed lattice structures for assessment of energy absorption efficiency.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Experimental results of compression tests of 3D-printed lattice structures for assessment of energy absorption efficiency.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Machine-readable text
- Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Scientists, engineers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until data will be published in article

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Project budget allocation: allocate part of the project budget for data curation, documentation, and long-term preservation.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Sergejs Tarasovs (0000-0001-5091-3770)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

The Zenodo repository will ensure that the data complies with the FAIR principles after the project is completed. No additional costs are required.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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